

SOP DNA extraction, purification, amplification, and sequencing of planktonic microbial communities in water samples.

1. Introduction and Scope

The main purpose of this SOP is to describe the analysis of planktonic microbial communities from water samples of selected locations of the Red River Delta and Cat Ba Island, Viet Nam. These are to be compared to the microbial communities that might be attached to microplastic particles found on the same sampling locations.

2. Principle of the Method

As previously described in the SOP “Water column collection, filtration, and sample storage for microbiological analyses of microplastics”, vacuum filtration will be used to separate and collect MPs and free-living microorganisms from water samples. For planktonic bacteria, water will be sampled from each listed location and depth (vol. depending on Vietnamese team bottles available), using a Niskin bottle. Nylon filters (NF, pore size 45 μm) will be used to collect debris over 45 μm in size, while membrane filters (MCE, pore size 0.22 μm) will be used to retain free-living bacteria from the water samples.

3. Chemicals and Reagents

- 70% EtOH (alcohol) for sterilisation of equipment.
- 0.2 M Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS)
- DNA extraction kit
- Nuclease-free water
- Agencourt Ampure XP purification Kit
- Qubit reagents
 - Standard 1 and 2
 - Working solution
- Minlon reagents
 - 16S Barcoding Kit1-24
 - Flow Cell PrimingKit
 - LongAmpHotStartTaq2XMasterMix
 - AgencourtAMPureXPbeads
 - 70% EtOH prepared with nuclease-free water.

4. Materials and Equipment

- Niskin bottles
- Buckets with lids (x 6)
- Cellulose nitrate membrane filters (0.22 μm pore size, ϕ 47 mm)
- Nylon filters (45 μm pore size, ϕ 47 mm)
- Flat tip tweezers
- Gloves
- Falcon tubes (50 mL) for concentrate storage
- Falcon tubes (15 mL) for filter storage
- Eppendorf tubes (5 mL)
- Eppendorf tubes (1.5 mL)
- Microcentrifuge tubes (0.5 mL)
- Microcentrifuge tubes (0.2 mL, thin-walled)
- Cooler with dry ice on board / fridge
- Freezer on facilities near sampling sites

- Vacuum filtration equipment (glass funnels, HDPE tubing, and pump)
- Stainless steel spatula / spoon
- Thermocycler
- Pipettes and pipette tips P2, P10, P20, P100, P200, P1000
- Micro centrifuge
- Qubit fluorometer
- Minlon Flow cell

5. Method for water collection and filtration

5.1 Water collection

- 5.1.1 Water (vol. depending on available Niskin bottles) from each location and depth will be sampled to concentrate planktonic microorganisms by deploying Niskin bottles at the following locations:
Refer to the [MicrobiologyUK-MolecularBiologyFieldSamples Nov22](#) for an updated version of samples names and locations.
- 5.1.2 Immediately upon retrieval, the content of the Niskin bottle will be poured into a clean, ethanol-wiped bucket of an appropriate volume, and closed with a lid until filtration. The Niskin bottle will be deployed again to obtain triplicates.
- 5.1.3 Water filtration will be performed on the boat, although it is expected that due to the large volume of water, the process will be slow and the samples will have to wait to be processed.

5.2 Water filtration

- 5.2.1 Before sample filtration, flat tweezers and vacuum filtration device will be wiped with 70% EtOH. Distilled water will be passed through before every experimental session.
- 5.2.2 Nylon net filters (pore size 45 µm) will be placed onto the filtration device, using flat tweezers, to remove debris from the sample, and the resulting filter will be discarded.
- 5.2.3 For each individual sample, water collected in the receiving flask from the vacuum filtration system will be transferred into a clean container after every filtration step required to filter the total collected volume (vol. depending on Niskin bottle).
- 5.2.4 The total resulting filtrated water (vol. depending on Niskin bottle) will then be filtered through a cellulose membrane filter (0.22 µm) to collect the free-living microorganisms. Water collected in the receiving flask will be discarded as often as required until the full sample volume has been filtered.
- 5.2.5 Filters will be stored in tubes and kept cold (4 °C) until stored at – 80°C or inside tubes with lysis buffer to be frozen at - 20°C.
- 5.2.6 Tubes will be labelled with location and depth of water filtered using a permanent waterproof tape. Separate tubes will be used for each filter.

5.3 DNA extraction

- 5.3.1 Depending on the extraction kit: A) insert the filter paper into a 5 mL bead tube; or B) if using a Ribolyser instrument for lysis, using a sterile forceps the filter will be transferred into sterile Petri dish. The filter will then be broken into 4 pieces with the pair of sterile forceps. Finally, using the sterile forceps, the pieces of filter will be transferred into 4 individual lysing tubes provided by the extraction kit.
- 5.3.2 The protocol provided by the extraction kit will be followed.
- 5.3.3 DNA extracts will be stored at – 80 °C until further amplification, purification, and sequencing using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon sequencing platform.

5.4 DNA quantification with Qubit

- 5.4.1 Prepare the Qubit dsDNA BR assay standards (2) and set up the required number of microcentrifuge tubes (0.5 mL) according to the number of DNA extracts to quantify. The top of the tubes will be labelled, making sure that the walls of the tube are clean for the fluorometric readings to work appropriately.
- 5.4.2 The protocol by the manufacturer will be followed. Briefly, Qubit working solution (180 - 199 μ L) will be added to each tube so that the final volume in each tube is 200 μ L.
- 5.4.3 Individual DNA extracts will be added to the corresponding tube with Qubit solution. Tubes will be incubated for 2 minutes, after which the standards and samples will be read.
- 5.4.4 The quality of the DNA extracts could be tested using a Nanodrop.

5.5 DNA amplification

- 5.5.1 Bacterial DNA will be amplified by PCR using universal bacterial primers (include barcodes to be used).
- 5.5.2 A PCR ready mix will be used, otherwise a master mix will be prepared with taq polymerase (0.1 μ L), forward and reverse primers (0.5 μ L each), dNTPs (2 μ L), magnesium chloride (2 μ L), ammonium (2 μ L). Quantities for a 50 μ L reaction.
- 5.5.3 Individual DNA extracts (5 μ L) will be placed in tubes containing the above quantities of the master mix, and topped up with dnase-free water to a final volume of 50 μ L to be amplified.
- 5.5.4 Tubes will be placed in a thermocycler and the appropriate cycle selected (likely, 4 min of initial denaturation at 95°C followed by 30 cycles of 1min denaturation at 95°C, 45 s for annealing at 55°C and 1 min of extension at 72°C. The final extension for 10 min at 72°C).
- 5.5.5 The amplified libraries will be purified using an Agencourt Ampure XP purification Kit, following the manufacturer's protocol.
- 5.5.6 Once the cycle is over, amplicons will be either stored at – 20 C or run in an agarose gel to verify the appropriate amplicon size (bp) was obtained.

5.6 DNA sequencing using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon sequencing platform.

- 5.6.1 Ribosomal RNA operons will be sequenced using the SQK-16S024 16s barcoding kit on Minlon Mk 1 R9 Version flow cells. The manufacturer's protocol will be followed. This is summarised below:
- 5.6.2 Individual sample 16S barcodes will be obtained from one of the respective 96-well plates (the 96-well plates are designed to break into strips of eight wells/barcodes, these can be removed from the plate at any one time.).
- 5.6.3 For each sample to be tested, the following mixture will be prepared in separate 0.2 mL PCR tubes: Nuclease-free water (5 μ L), input DNA (10 ng), LongAmpHotStart Taq2XMasterMix (25 μ L).
- 5.6.4 The required barcodes will be added to the individual tubes prepared in the previous step. Notes will be taken of which barcode number corresponds to each sample.
- 5.6.5 The input DNA will be amplified following a selected cycle in the thermocycle.
- 5.6.6 The amplicons will be purified using the AMPureXP kit following the manufacturer's protocol.
- 5.6.7 The purified amplicons will be quantified using a Qubit fluorometer as previously described.
- 5.6.8 Barcoded libraries will be pooled to a total of 50 – 100 fmoles in 10 μ l of 10 mM Tris-HCl with 50 mM NaCl.
- 5.6.9 RAP (1 μ L) will be added to the pooled libraries, and the reaction incubated for 5 mins.
- 5.6.10 To load and prime the flow cell, the sequencing buffer (SQB), flush tether (FLT) and flush buffer (FB) tubes will be mixed by vortexing and spinning down.
- 5.6.11 The flow cell will be placed onto the MinION Mk 1B
- 5.6.12 The priming mix previously prepared will be added (800 μ L) into the flow cell.

- 5.6.13 The library for loading will be prepared by mixing SQB (34 uL), loading buffer (LB, 25.5 uL), nuclease-free water (4.5 uL), and the DNA library (11 uL).
- 5.6.14 The prepared library will be added (75 uL) to the flow cell, ensuring that this flows into the port.
- 5.6.15 The library is ready for sequencing.

5.7 Bioinformatic analysis

- 5.7.1 Fast5 files will be base called using the Guppy software (3.2.2), sized between 3700 and 5700 bp in length, separated by barcode, and then screened by Discontinuous Megablast against the EZ BioCloud 16S rRNA gene database using Geneious (11.1.5).23.
- 5.7.2 Best BLAST hits (BBH) will be exported as csv files and organized using pivot tables in Excel.
- 5.7.3 Further community analysis will be done using Mothur, Primer7 and the R-package Vegan.
- 5.7.4 MinION sequence reads will be made available in NCBI.

6 Documentation

Clear labelling of the tubes will be required. The labels need to include location, depth, and date of collection.

7 Safety

[Risk Assessment.](#)

8 References

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[Oxford Nanopore Technologies website](#)